

Electric Structures Influence on the Atmospheric Spiral Vortices Stability

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Abstract

Observations, which demonstrate the important role of electromagnetic forces in dynamics of powerful atmospheric spiral vortices, are presented. The mechanisms of helical motion generation in the presence of plasma-like charged subsystems are considered. Some conclusions are formulated.

1. Introduction

The nature of tropical cyclones (TC) has been systematically investigated for more than 160 years. But, in spite of remarkable progress in the given area of study, the situation remains still far from development of these phenomena exhaustive algorithmic theory. Basically, researches develop hydrodynamic theories of TC. However, in spite of some possibilities of short-term trajectory forecast, they do not answer on the number of key questions concerned with mechanisms of the TC origin and their following intensification, the maintenance of their stationary phase, with the presence of geographic, temporal and other asymmetries. The role of electromagnetic phenomena in TC dynamics is not sufficiently described in the literature in spite of the extensive charged regions in the TC structure and strong electromagnetic fields inside TC and tornado were founded in numerous observations [1-3].

The evaluations performed in papers [4,5] have demonstrated an important role of electromagnetic forces in the generation of gas in-flow to the TC axis, in the particles flying, i.e. in production of updraft flows and a cloud structure observed appearance.

The basic purposes of this paper are as the follows:

- to attract the researcher's attention to some observational data related to the role of the Earth's magnetic field and electromagnetic phenomena in TC which have been discussed not sufficiently in conventional theories; and
- to study the electromagnetic forces contribution to the helical flows generation in TC necessary for the further development of unstable atmosphere self-organization concept.

2. Some typhoogenesis observational data

We present here some observational data indicating the possible role of electromagnetic factors in large-scale atmospheric phenomena under study [4]. Firstly, the geographic asymmetry of typhoogenesis must be mentioned. It means that the average number of tropical cyclones arised at the northern hemisphere is twice that the analogous number of TC appeared at the southern hemisphere. Though separation on eastern and western hemispheres is a pure conventional one, from the hydrodynamical viewpoint, nevetherless there exists the clear asymmetry of typhoonogenesis namely: TC are forming in the eastern hemisphere twice frequently

as in the western one. Generally speaking, the region of TC origin does not placed at the near-equatorial zone, but most likely it is at intersection of the near-equatorial zone with the near-equatorial geomagnetic region (which means that there exists probably a threshold on the vertical component of geomagnetic field).

The typical horizontal scales of TC in Atlantic ocean and in Pacific one are quite different (and they are in inverse correlation with the local value of geomagnetic field). Many TC arise in the middle of trade-wind zone with the quite homogeneous air mass. So the claims about large initial moment and temperature contrasts in the convergence region necessary to generate TC isn't confirmed by observations.

The statement on the unique mechanism for TC rotation maintenance through the contact of air mass with ocean surface is incorrect. Because tropical cyclones may exist within a long time even after its going into land and many TC's disappear over an ocean. Besides, the rotation of opposite direction (an anticyclon motion over a typhoon) is observed above TC. So this rotation is generated without any contact with the ocean surface. If the pure hydrodynamical mechanism for rotational moment of TC would take place only, then large enough existing initial vortexes could be intensified. So in the both hemispheres TC must be observed with clockwise rotation and counterclockwise one. But it is not the case: the direction of air rotation in TC is fixed for each hemisphere (nothern and southern ones). Consequently, there must exist the mechanism for maintenance of the fixed spatial structure of the TC-phenomena which isn't taken into account by the conventional hydrodynamical model.

Then the funnel of a tornado goes down from above. It means that no contact of an aerodynamical flow with an ocean is needed to generate the powerful vortice. Note here that TC grows also not from the ocean surface, but it "goes down" from above. The maximal tangential velocity inside TC is observed at some altitude, and the another mechanism for generation of the anticyclonic rotation exists at some other more higher altitude. These mechanisms action altitudes are located near the regions having electric charges of opposite signs. Possibly, charged particles (tending to move to the Earth poles) influence on the atmospheric flows at the top of TC (which are neither random in direction, not axially symmetric). As a rule, the axis of cyclone or anticyclone is not vertical, but it possesses a large pitch to the Earth surface. Remember that the geomagnetic field is also inclined to the Earth surface and charged region tends to possess their rotation axis along the magnetic field. In fact, the rotation axis pitch, the precession and the system movement as a whole are determined by several factors, so-called a hydrodynamic rotating subsystem, connected with the Earth surface at the vortice bottom and with a some appropriate flow at the vortice top, and a rotating charged subsystem which tends to move according to EMHD-laws in self-consistent inhomogeneous electric and magnetic fields. Since TC has two oppositely charged regions simultaneously, its axis becomes practically vertical. It can be conditioned by electric forces, which cause the system symmetry by arranging the oppositely charged rotating regions one above other.

3. Plasma-like systems dynamics and helicity generation

The magnitude of electromagnetic forces for charged regions is of the same order of typical hydrodynamic forces like the pressure gradient one. Therefore, electromagnetic forces must be taken into account under TC studying. The value and direction of the net force may be arbitrary in the dependence on the value of charges, currents and other parameters of TC, including its position on the Earth. That is the reason that 47 percent of TC possess the classical parabolic trajectory only. For MHD-mechanism contributions to TC dynamics the evaluations

give negligible small values. Therefore, it is necessary to consider EMHD-mechanisms. In doing so, the Coulomb forces must be taken into account, and the main currents will be convective ones produced by moving charged regions, but not conductivity currents. The plasma model with magnetic fields can be introduced as a useful qualitative model to describe the TC-phenomenon (let us remember spontaneous origin of rotation in the plasma L-H transition). In this case a large speed of system self-rotation can be established. It is essential that the mechanism will work at the presence of some fraction of free charges also, but not for fully ionized plasma only. So the TC toroidal structure with the typhoon eye can be easily explained [4].

Generally speaking, besides the direct model of electromagnetic forces influence on charged regions movement in TC it must be pointed out the following. Taking into account the real atmosphere stratification in TC and additional forces in charged regions, then it is necessary to sew together analytical solutions on corresponding boundaries. So it can be observed wave reflections, resonance wave regimes etc. As the result, TC can interchange energy (in the both vertical directions) with the ionosphere (it is the open system) through IGW (internal gravity waves) and quasistationary electromagnetic waves. For example, the ionosphere is a possible candidate through which the observed strange interactions of TCs in two hemispheres hydrodynamically separated by the equator may occur.

Usually, in model theories the medium dielectric constant and turbulent viscosity are supposed to be constant. However, in reality these characteristics are variable, for example, they are modulated by the structure of TC itself. This important fact can help for further development of the atmosphere self-organization concept.

Two interesting questions arise now [5]:

- 1) What does the contribution is given by electromagnetic forces in the average hydrodynamic helicity?
- 2) How do they modulate the value of helicity?

Note that the hydrodynamical helicity $H_t = \langle \mathbf{v} \text{ curl } \mathbf{v} \rangle$ can influence on the development and stability of hydrodynamic systems. Therefore, the usage of this characteristic is productive for describing the self-organization process. Parallel with the integral helicity H_t , the helicity density can be of the physical interest:

$$H = v_r \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial v_z}{\partial \varphi} - \frac{\partial v_\varphi}{\partial z} \right) + v_\varphi \left(\frac{\partial v_r}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial v_z}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{v_z}{r} \left(\frac{\partial(r v_\varphi)}{\partial r} - \frac{\partial v_r}{\partial \varphi} \right).$$

Sometimes these three terms are named as the appropriate components of helicity H_r , H_φ , H_z . Since the helicity is not a characteristics of fixed sign, then the same mechanisms can lead to the redistribution, dissipation, or generation of the helicity.

A rough estimations of the average helicity for the atmosphere at rest gives the its typical value of the order of 10^{-4} m/c^2 (or smaller) due to the Earth rotation (the Coriolis force action) and the natural convection. It is well known [6] that average components of helicity are evaluated for the β -hurricane as $H_z \sim 10^{-3} \text{ m/c}^2$, $H_\varphi \sim 10^{-1} \text{ m/c}^2$. If we devide the TC region into 4 subregions conventionally (the boundary layer, the eye wall, the central part and the region of outflow) and evaluate the helicity density with usage of everage motions for TC quasistationary stage, then the average helicity density can reach the value of 0.3 m/c^2 and more.

However, all depends also on spatial scales of the average performed, in particular, the account of real motions (not averaging axisymmetric ones) gives calculated magnitudes by the one order larger [7] and the helicity volume density becomes inhomogeneous significantly. Moreover it varies in different regions of TC by few orders of a magnitude, sometimes up to its sign change. Different components of the helicity are frequently to be close one to other in their magnitude modulus but they have opposite signs. So in the given region of TC the vortices with definite rotation direction are survived.

The estimate of Coriolis force influence on the helicity magnitude gives, for the developed TC case, smaller amplitudes in the comparison with observed ones (differences vary from few times up to few orders of magnitude). Besides, in TC the helicity volume density hasn't the cylindrical symmetry. For example, observations are showing that in spiral rainbands and in neighbouring to them regions the helicity volume density may differs by its sign. Therefore the helical motions (so-called horizontal vortices) are observed also into spiral rainbands.

Thus, it is necessary to find forces responsible for the helicity excess and to consider additional mechanisms causing both the nonsymmetric helicity spatial distribution in the TC-periphery and its generation. Possibly, electromagnetic forces play this role. They give the contribution to the average horizontal rotation which differs by the sign for charge regions placed at the altitude of the order of 6 km and at the altitude about 12 km. But if we take into account that the Earth magnetic field is inclined to the vertical direction and a charged subsystem tends to have their rotation axis close to the magnetic field direction then charged region branches (with vortices having the horizontal component of rotation) are developed at the TC boundary and resulting to the system cylindrical symmetry disturbances because, for example, charged subsystems in two spiral bands placed at the opposite sides of TC will tend to have the same direction of rotation with the rotation axis directed to the Earth magnetic field pole. Therefore, the helicity volume density distribution, for example, in TC spiral bands will be inhomogeneous not only on the radius and the altitude but on the rotation angle also.

Calculations show that in TC the helicity components H_r , H_ϕ have the magnitude modulus maximum but their signs are opposite. So they are in the competition one to other in the full helicity production. For the case of TC charged subsystems the main contribution to these helicity components give electromagnetic forces.

The description of helicity generation in TC may be given on the basis of turbulent EMHD flows where the source of turbulence production is modelled by the homogeneous isotropic random force \mathbf{f} . In the reference system locally rotating along vertical axis z with frequency $\Omega(\mathbf{r},z)$ (the average rotation is single out) the basic equations are written with usage of alfvén variables and it is supposed that the Earth magnetic field \mathbf{B}_0 is homogeneous in the TC region. So the average magnetic field is also single out.

If we are interested the pulsations contribution to the average helicity generation $H = \langle \mathbf{u} \mathbf{w} \rangle$ and $\mathbf{w} = \text{curl } \mathbf{u}$, it is necessary to single out all average hydrodynamical terms and take into account ones having the same order of magnitude. For the viscosity it is necessary to take the turbulent one because it accounts the important influence of high order correlation terms on large-scale motions in the vortice. Besides, for the typical scales during calculations of all type derivatives we must take the large-scale characteristics because the pulsations contribution to large-scale processes is of our interest. In the first approximation we use the hydrodynamical equation for helicity volume density:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \mathbf{u} \mathbf{w} \rangle = & - \langle \mathbf{w} (\mathbf{u} \nabla) \mathbf{u} \rangle - 2 \langle \mathbf{w} [\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{u}] \rangle - 2 \langle \mathbf{u} \text{curl} [\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{u}] \rangle - \langle \mathbf{u} \text{curl} [(\mathbf{u} \nabla) \mathbf{u}] \rangle - \nu \langle \mathbf{w} \text{curl} \mathbf{w} \rangle - \\ & - \nu \langle \mathbf{u} \text{curl} (\text{curl} \mathbf{w}) \rangle + \frac{\langle \mathbf{f} \mathbf{w} \rangle}{\rho} + \frac{\langle \mathbf{u} \text{curl} \mathbf{f} \rangle}{\rho} - \frac{\langle \mathbf{w} \nabla P' \rangle}{\rho}, \end{aligned}$$

where P' denotes the pressure pulsations, ν denotes the kinematic viscosity and we add terms taking into account the charged subsystem presence. Let us consider the helicity H_e generation by electromagnetic forces at the background of the given established hydrodynamical helicity. Besides our estimates show that electrodynamical terms are the main one in equations derived. Therefore their contribution to the self-organization mechanism of large-scale cyclogenesis will be the most essential. Now taking into account the largest terms we obtain the following equation describing the helicity generation at large-scales:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} H_e = - \frac{2q^2}{\rho\lambda} \langle \mathbf{u} \mathbf{w} \rangle + \frac{cq}{\sqrt{4\pi\rho\lambda}} \langle \mathbf{w} \text{curl} \mathbf{h} \rangle + \frac{cq}{\sqrt{4\pi\rho\lambda}} \text{grad} q \langle [\text{curl} \mathbf{h} \times \mathbf{u}] \rangle - \frac{\sqrt{4\pi\rho}}{\rho c} q \nu_m \langle \mathbf{u} \Delta \mathbf{h} \rangle + 2 \langle \mathbf{f} \mathbf{w} \rangle,$$

where q denotes the volume electric charge density, \mathbf{h} denotes the magnetic field perturbation, λ denotes the medium conductivity, ν_m denotes the magnetic viscosity.

Let us suppose now that the volume charge density is the given function and use it as the background characteristics of electrical subsystems to study the helicity generation by electromagnetic forces. It is obviously that the first term determines the helicity damping and it will restricts the helicity growth.

It is possible to investigate the behaviour of correlation term and three other ones which directly depend on the presence of charged particles in the system considered:

$$\frac{cq}{\sqrt{4\pi\rho\lambda}} \langle \mathbf{w} \text{curl} \mathbf{h} \rangle, \quad \frac{cq}{\sqrt{4\pi\rho\lambda}} \text{grad} q \langle [\text{curl} \mathbf{h} \times \mathbf{u}] \rangle, \quad - \frac{\sqrt{4\pi\rho}}{\rho c} q \nu_m \langle \mathbf{u} \Delta \mathbf{h} \rangle.$$

The first term and the third one will change their sign under the charge density sign changing. Consequently, they are participating in the maintenance of system inhomogeneous spatial structure and its helicity generation properties. For a some given gas flow and the volume charge density sign they may cause the helicity generation but for the case of opposite volume charge density sign these terms will decrease the saturation level of helicity generation in system.

The dependence of second term on charge density gradient determines more fine spatial structure of the helicity generation in tropical cyclones, for example it may take place in the typhoon eye wall or in the TC rainbands.

For each term it is easy to write the corresponding equations taking into account the most important contributions only:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \mathbf{w} \text{curl} \mathbf{h} \rangle = \nu_m \langle \mathbf{w} \Delta \text{curl} \mathbf{h} \rangle + \frac{cq}{\sqrt{4\pi\rho\lambda}} \langle \mathbf{w} \text{curl} \mathbf{w} \rangle - \frac{c}{\sqrt{4\pi\rho\lambda}} \langle \mathbf{w} \cdot (\text{grad} q \nabla) \mathbf{u} \rangle + \frac{c}{\sqrt{4\pi\rho\lambda}} \langle \mathbf{w} \cdot (\mathbf{u} \nabla) (\nabla q) \rangle,$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle [\text{curl} \mathbf{h} \times \mathbf{u}] \rangle = \nu_m \langle [\Delta \text{curl} \mathbf{h} \times \mathbf{u}] \rangle + \frac{c}{\sqrt{4\pi\rho\lambda}} \langle [\text{curl} (\text{curl} q \mathbf{u}) \times \mathbf{u}] \rangle,$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \mathbf{u} \Delta \mathbf{h} \rangle = \nu_m \langle \mathbf{u} \Delta \Delta \mathbf{h} \rangle - \frac{c}{\sqrt{4\pi\rho\lambda}} \langle \mathbf{u} \text{curl} \{ \text{curl} (\text{curl} q \mathbf{u}) \} \rangle.$$

and then calculate them using Furutsu-Novikov-Donsker formula to convert correlators in more simple form like given below:

$$\left\langle \frac{\delta u_k(\mathbf{k}, \omega)}{\delta f_m(\mathbf{k}', \omega')} \right\rangle = \frac{\Pi_{km} \delta(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}') \delta(\omega - \omega') k^2}{\left\{ \left(-i\omega + \nu k^2 + \frac{q^2}{\lambda \rho} \right) k^2 + \frac{i q}{\rho \lambda} k \text{grad}_k q \right\}}, \quad \Pi_{km} = \delta_{km} - \frac{k_k k_m}{k^2}.$$

The correlator will be determined now by the following expression:

$$\langle \mathbf{f} \mathbf{w} \rangle = \frac{\tau_{cor}}{\tau} \frac{\rho \lambda}{q |\text{grad} q|} \int_0^\infty \text{arctg}\{\alpha\} G(k) |k| dk, \quad \alpha = \frac{2\tau^2 q |k| |\text{grad} q| (\nu k^2 \rho \lambda + q^2)}{\tau^2 q^2 |\text{grad} q|^2 + k^2 \rho^2 \lambda^2 - \tau^2 k^2 (\nu k^2 \rho \lambda + q^2)^2}.$$

Taking now in this expression suitable, physically reasonable model functions for $G(k)$, for example, $G(k) = A \lambda^4 k^n \exp(-\lambda^2 k^2) \sin(\Lambda k)$, $n = 3$, it is possible to obtain numerical values. Here A – is the normalization constant and the incoming typical scale Λ must be founded from the following condition $\langle \mathbf{f} \mathbf{w} \rangle_q|_{q=0} = 0$.

4. Discussion

Calculations show that the presence of plasma-like subsystems in TC results to the appearance of new channels of helicity generation which are additional ones to early known, in particular, the generation due to shear flows (for example, conditioned by the inhomogeneous rotation), the average magnetic field presence (the mechanism connected with Alfvén waves) and so on. The new terms are dependent on the charge density sign. So they together with the standard hydrodynamical terms may cause the threshold of helicity generation in the system considered (in the dependence on charge density sign). Therefore, it results to the forming of self-maintenant spatial structure of powerful atmospheric vortices.

Besides the number of terms are dependent on the charge density gradient. So this leads to the appearance in helicity generation additional asymmetries (at the different sides of charge density maximum the helicity behaviour will has distinctions). All these features change essentially the system properties especially in the typhoon eye wall and spiral bands. As a whole, the charged subsystems in TC influence significantly on intense vortex parameters and they promote to support well defined structure of wind flows. Besides it is follows from the equations derived that charged subsystems of large-scale vortex modulate its turbulent characteristics. More rigorous quantitative analysis of these processes is very perspective to further development of self-organization concept for the large-scale atmospheric tropical cyclogenesis.

5. Conclusion

Thus electromagnetic phenomena may play the significant role in large-scale atmospheric crisis processes like tropical cyclones: electromagnetic forces take part in the maintenance of TC inhomogeneous structure observed and they influence on atmospheric motions in TC. The electromagnetic forces influence significantly also on the helicity generation and promote the clear hierarchy of gas motions in vortices. So the full description of TC dynamics requires to take into account the presence of plasma-like subsystems and their dynamics.

References

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